

Green Marketing- The Next Big thing: The Impact of it in Consumer Behavior due to Variation in Prices

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Abstract

The concept of Green Marketing is still in the stage of infancy. Even till date, it has not been inculcated as a subject in identifying the key ideas in relation to the awareness of green products that may be most relevant to the eco-friendly environment. This paper will attempt to identify the extent to which consumers are concerned to purchase green products, to study the various factors which affect consumers purchasing green products, to evaluate attitudes of consumers regarding green products, to analyze the demographics of the consumers inclined to purchase eco-friendly products that are presumed to be environmentally preferable. This type of marketing incorporates a broad range of activities involving product modifications, changes in the production process and as well as the type of machines used while manufacturing. Green marketing is never a simple task to take on and lead the market. It is to be tried, practiced and inculcated by the society to set the trend. Green marketing is also known as environmental marketing or eco marketing which is healthy and contains some powerful green features which can reduce diseases in large number. Let us hopefully believe that green markets flourish and take a stand.

Introduction

The business environment is ever-changing. To compete in this dynamic environment, businesses have to constantly upgrade themselves to keep up with the most attractive trends. One such trend that has been hitting the headlines recently is the concept of green marketing. With the words such as global warming, ozone depletion, and carbon footprints becoming common terminology, it is natural for the society to become more and more environmentally conscious resulting in businesses entering the ‘green market’. Although organizations see Green Marketing as a new business strategy, the term came into prominence a few decades ago in the 1980s. Green Marketing refers to the process of marketing products based on their environmental benefits. The product itself can be an eco-friendly one or can involve an eco-friendly production process, sustainable packaging or advertising. The world is rapidly changing where there are substitutes for everything. We have started banning plastics, but still, we are dependent on it in our daily life. The profit-minded

manufacturers are putting nil efforts, but those who think or those who are environmentally active are trying to bring in some awareness to the people regarding the Green products.

The chaos is how the prices of the different products are going to vary while we hit green. How far the consumers are going to accept the product, the process, the promotion and importantly the prices? Will the customers be satisfied with all the marketing elements of a Green Product? Is this really a problem in the economy?

Let us look into this to analyze how different groups of people have reacted on this:

History of Green Marketing

Only in the eighties and early nineties, the term Green Marketing came into prominence, whose proceedings resulted in one of the first books on green marketing titled “Ecological Marketing”.

Ice cream seller Ben & Jerry’s financial report was supplemented by a greater view on the company’s environmental impact. This led to the start of the Corporate Social Responsibility Reports.

A document prepared by the World Commission on Environment and Development in 1987 defined sustainable development as meeting “the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own need”. This was another step towards widespread thinking on sustainability in everyday activity and became known as the Brundtland Report.

Two remarkable milestones for the primary wave of green marketing came in the form of published books: Green Marketing by Ken Peattie, 1992, in the United Kingdom and Green Marketing: Challenges & Opportunities for the New Marketing Age by Jacquelyn Ottman, 1993 in the United States of America.

According to Jacquelyn Ottman, author of “The New Rules of Green Marketing: Strategies, Tools, and Inspiration for Sustainable Branding”, from an organizational point of view, environmental considerations should be integrated into all aspects of marketing, being new product development, communications and all points in between.

Although the “Green consumerism” movements in the U.S. and other countries have struggled to reach critical mass and influence, public opinion polls taken since the late 1980s have shown consistently that a significant percentage of consumers worldwide profess a strong willingness to favor environmentally conscious and beneficial products and organizations. According to Joel Makower, a writer on green marketing, one of green marketing’s challenges is the lack of standards or public consensus about what constitutes “green”. This lack of consensus by consumers, marketers, activists, regulators, and influential people has hindered the growth of green products because companies are often reluctant to promote their green attributes, and consumers are often skeptical about claims.

Irrespective of these challenges, there seems to be an increase in the no. of enthusiasts for Green Marketing, particularly due to growing global concern about climate change. This concern has led more companies to advertise their commitment to curtail the impacts on climate, and the impact that it is having on their merchandise and services.

Objectives

1. To study the awareness of consumers about the Green initiatives.
2. To analyze consumer behavior if green features are established.
3. To determine the willingness of people to Go Green.

Opportunities

1. Free from pollution
2. Profitable environment
3. Diseases can be reduced
4. Conservation of resources

Challenges

1. High in prices
2. Lack of standardization
3. People are unaware
4. Water treatment technology is required

Review of Literature

Author: Ken Peattie in the year 1993

In the last two decades, the burgeoning environmental movement was termed as the “green movement”. The author also called the consumers who are environmentally aware as “greenconsumers”. According to him, the “green products” were produced to protect the environment. He also mentioned that green marketing has replaced conventional marketing.

Author: Polonsky and Rosenberger in the year 2001

According to the author, Green marketing covers the entire marketing activities undertaken by firms as they develop the manufacturing of products that have a positive impact on the environment. They also reduce the negative side of the environment. Green marketing has grown widely by adopting the techniques of packaging and presentation of products.

Author: Kim in the year 2011

According to Kim, the study shows that environmental attitude is a significant determinant of green purchase behavior. The ecological consumption of consumers is actually determined by their involvement in rectifying the environmental problems. The research also shows that consumers are willing to pay the premium price or extra cost to purchase wood products.

Research Methodology

Convenient sampling technique has been used to collect the samples. Various sectors like the employed, the unemployed, the retired and the students have been considered for the study. The data is collected through a questionnaire, which was circulated among different age groups and statuses.

Analysis, Interpretation and Further Findings

The data collected represents respondents of various sections namely employed, unemployed, students and retired people of whom 59% are male respondents and 41% are female respondents.

Female respondents are more fully aware of the green products than male respondents. It is found that social networking plays an important role in creating awareness about green products.

Most of the respondents' willingness to pay a high price for green features depends mainly on the product. However, a respectable amount of employed sector is willing to pay high irrespective of other factors.

Although the majority of the respondents feel neutral about whether enough information about green features is provided to them while purchasing a product, a decent number of respondents feel that adequate information is not provided to them.

Where, on the whole, the majority seem to cite a reason for their willingness to pay high, as these products being pollution-free there seems to be a slight difference of opinion among the various sectors. Most of the students cite the reason as being pollution-free while most employed also cite conservation of resources as the main reason.

In general, the majority seems to be neutral on what makes them unwilling to pay more, but the employed sector firmly believes that unawareness of people is the main reason for the same, which is also supported by the retired and the students who are following them.

Respondents at a certain level, believe, on the whole, that green products have been headlines for really bringing a change while the student sector alone by a slight margin believe that it is plastics being slowly banned across the country.

People to an adequate extent credit the product itself as the high influence element for the buying behavior shown regarding the green products.

An overwhelming majority of the people accept that green products are healthy and are of good quality. They are neutral about the fragrance of the products and regarding their reasonability in pricing.

While the students seem to be satisfied with the available eco-friendly products on a superior level, the employed and the other sectors show just a competent level of satisfaction as many feel neutral about the situation.

The entire population shows a strong affirmation regarding their readiness to GO GREEN, irrespective of the income level of the sector they belong to.

Suggestions

1. Print on Recycled Paper
2. Invest in Online Marketing
3. Promote Local Vendors
4. Operate Fuel Efficient Vehicles
5. Environmental Donations and Charities

Conclusion

Being in the phase where societal marketing is of utmost importance, the organization considers what the society actually requires and what will be accepted now and in the future. According to the research, we can conclude that consumers are ready to Go Green. The business owners can also involve themselves in bringing a change in the society by taking a few more steps in reaching the ecological succession.

The steps can be

1. Taking eco-friendly papers and inks for printing the needed.
2. Practicing responsible waste disposal
3. Making the package process eco-friendly
4. Using eco-friendly power sources
5. Keeping the production environment clean
6. Effective and efficient shipping methods
7. Establishing steps to offset the environmental impact

Instead of considering Green marketing as another approach to marketing, it should be pursued with greater vigor as it has societal and environmental dimensions. The new mantra of success and growth is Sustainable development through Green marketing. Let us all join hands together to protect not only our country but also the earth.